

Information Literacy skills and Information Security Awareness of Undergraduate Students in Northern Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Background: This study explored the relationship between information literacy skills and information security awareness among undergraduate students in Northern Nigeria. Growing concerns about cyber threats, coupled with the critical role of information literacy in academic and personal development, highlight the importance of understanding how students' literacy skills influence their security awareness.

Objective: The objectives were to examine the level of information literacy skills of undergraduate students, ascertain their awareness of information security, and determine the relationship between literacy skills and security awareness.

Methods: The study adopted a quantitative, cross-sectional survey design. The population comprised 266,295 undergraduate students from federal universities in North-West Nigeria. A multistage sampling technique was employed: purposive sampling to select universities, followed by stratified random sampling to ensure representation. A total of 346 students were sampled. Out of the 346 questionnaires distributed, 236 valid responses were retrieved, giving a response rate of 68.2%. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, including correlation and regression analysis.

Findings: Findings showed that 84.8% of students could recognize the need for information resources, while 90.3% distinguished between potential resources. However, only 18.7% identified different methods of accessing information, and a mere 3.2% demonstrated the ability to synthesize and build on existing knowledge. Regarding information security, 63.1% could recognize phishing attempts, 64.8% were aware of data privacy issues, and 68.2% understood secure browsing practices. Conversely, only 58.9% appreciated the importance of system updates, and 44.5% were confident in using antivirus or encryption tools. Regression analysis revealed a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.772$, $p < 0.01$) between information literacy and information security awareness, indicating that higher literacy skills significantly enhance security practices.

Implication: The results underscore the urgent need for universities to integrate advanced information literacy and information security training into their curricula. Enhancing these competencies will not only support academic success but also strengthen students' resilience against evolving digital threats.

Conclusion: The study concludes that while students demonstrate foundational strengths in information literacy and basic security practices, significant gaps persist in higher-order literacy and advanced security measures.

Recommendation: It is recommended that universities embed advanced information literacy and information security modules into LIS and general education programs. Additionally, hands-on workshops should be offered on phishing recognition, password management, software updates, and data protection. Continuous digital learning opportunities should also be fostered to better equip students for future security challenges.

Keywords: Information Literacy, Information Security, Security Awareness, Information Systems, Password Management, Phishing Awareness, Data Privacy

INTRODUCTION

In the digital age, university students have become increasingly reliant on information systems for a myriad of academic and personal activities. This growing dependence has necessitated a robust understanding of information literacy—defined as the ability to effectively find, evaluate, and use information. For these digital natives, mastering information literacy is crucial not only for academic success but also for navigating and safeguarding their online presence. The rise of information systems and digital platforms has brought to light the pressing need for comprehensive information literacy to protect against security threats.

Information literacy, according to Iriani and Wicaksono (2021) encompasses a range of skills critical for interacting with digital environments effectively. It involves not just the ability to locate and retrieve information, but also to critically evaluate and apply it. In the context of university students, these skills are essential as they frequently engage with various forms of digital content, including academic resources, social media, and online communication tools. Despite their digital proficiency, students often lack the depth of knowledge required to handle security issues effectively, such as managing passwords, recognizing phishing attempts, and ensuring data privacy.

The intersection of information literacy and information security awareness is an area of significant concern (Kock, Berbekova and Assaf, 2021). The proliferation of digital threats, such as malware, phishing attacks, and identity theft, highlights the need for students to possess strong information literacy skills to safeguard their personal and academic data. This study seeks to explore this relationship by assessing how well students' information literacy correlates with their awareness and implementation of information security practices. Understanding this link can provide insights into whether improved information literacy can enhance security awareness and practices among students.

Statistical analysis techniques, particularly correlation analysis, will be employed to examine the relationship between students' information literacy and their security awareness. By surveying a representative sample of university students in Northern Nigeria, this study aims to measure their proficiency in finding, evaluating and using information and to relate these skills to their security practices. The findings of this study are expected to reveal whether higher information literacy is

associated with better information security practices, such as more effective password management and greater awareness of phishing threats.

Given the rapid evolution of digital threats and the increasing role of information systems in students' lives, it is important that educational institutions address these challenges. This research shows the importance of incorporating information literacy training into university curricula. By doing so, universities can better prepare students to direct the complications of the digital world and protect themselves against evolving security threats.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Information literacy has become a fundamental skill for individuals in the digital age, particularly for university students who are frequent users of information systems. In well-resourced educational environments, students are equipped with comprehensive training in information literacy, which includes the ability to locate, evaluate, and effectively use information (Bashorun, Bashorun and Akinbowale, 2021). This education not only supports their academic success but also enhances their ability to navigate digital environments securely. As a result, students in these settings exhibit a high level of awareness regarding information security practices, such as password management, phishing recognition, and data privacy, thereby safeguarding their personal and academic information from digital threats.

However, undergraduate students in northern Nigeria face a significant challenge in achieving similar levels of information literacy and security awareness (Muhammad, 2022). Despite the increasing reliance on digital platforms for academic and personal activities (Suleiman, n.d.), there is a noticeable gap in the integration of information literacy and security training within the educational framework. Many students demonstrate adequate skills in locating and using information but lack sufficient knowledge and practices related to information security. This deficiency leaves them vulnerable to digital threats and undermines their ability to protect themselves and their information effectively.

This study aims to address this problem by empirically assessing the relationship between information literacy and information security awareness among undergraduate students in Northern Nigeria. By surveying students' proficiency in information literacy and their awareness of security practices, the research will identify the correlation between these factors. The findings will provide valuable insights into the current state of information security awareness and highlight the need for improved information literacy training. The study will recommend strategies for integrating comprehensive information literacy and security training into the university curriculum, thereby enhancing students' ability to protect themselves in the digital environment.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

1. To examine the level of information literacy among university students, specifically their ability to locate, evaluate, and effectively use information within various information systems.
2. To determine undergraduate students' level of awareness of information security practices, including password management, phishing awareness, and data privacy.

HYPOTHESIS

H₁ There is significant relationship between information literacy skills of undergraduate students and the information security initiatives taken.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Information literacy is a crucial skill set that enables individuals to effectively locate, evaluate, and use information. The concept has evolved significantly over the past few decades, influenced by the rapid expansion of digital technologies and the increasing complexity of information environments. Traditionally, information literacy focused on basic research skills, but today it encompasses a broader range of competencies, including critical thinking and digital literacy. According to the American Library Association (2000), information literacy is essential for academic success and lifelong learning, reflecting the ability to navigate an ever-expanding information landscape.

Several theoretical frameworks underpin the concept of information literacy. The "Big6" model by Mike Eisenberg and Bob Berkowitz (1990) is one such framework that outlines a systematic approach to information problem-solving. This model emphasizes six key stages: task definition, information seeking strategies, location and access, use of information, synthesis, and evaluation. Additionally, the "Information search Process model" developed by Carol Kuhlthau (2000) offers a comprehensive definition of information literacy, focusing on the ability to identify, locate, evaluate, and use information effectively. These frameworks provide a foundation for understanding the multifaceted nature of information literacy and its importance in academic and professional contexts, (Kamba and Buba, 2022; Buba, Song, and Abdullahi, 2021).

In higher education, information literacy is increasingly recognized as a critical component of academic success. Studies have shown that students who possess strong information literacy skills are better equipped to conduct research, analyze information, and produce high-quality academic work (Odede and Zawedde, 2018). University libraries and academic programs often incorporate information literacy training into their curricula to help students develop these skills. However, there is variability in the implementation and effectiveness of such programs, with some institutions providing comprehensive training and others offering limited support (Bashorun, Bashorun & Akinbowale, 2021). This inconsistency highlights the need for standardized approaches to information literacy instruction.

The rise of digital technologies has transformed the landscape of information literacy. Digital information literacy involves not only traditional research skills but also the ability to navigate digital platforms, evaluate online sources, and understand digital rights and responsibilities (Iriani & Wicaksono, 2021). The widespread availability of digital content and the increasing use of social media have introduced new challenges, such as information overload and the spread of misinformation. Research by Marlini (2019) emphasizes the need for students to develop critical digital literacy skills to effectively manage and assess digital information. Despite this, many educational institutions have yet to fully integrate digital literacy into their information literacy programs.

A study of the existing research reveals that while significant progress has been made in defining and understanding information literacy, challenges remain in its implementation and assessment. Studies consistently highlight the importance of information literacy for academic success and digital competency. However, gaps exist in the uniformity of information literacy training across different educational settings and the integration of digital literacy components. Additionally, there is a need for more research on the impact of information literacy on specific outcomes, such as information security awareness and academic performance.

The review shows that, there is limited research on the effectiveness of information literacy programs in diverse educational contexts, particularly in regions with limited resources. While digital literacy is increasingly recognized as a critical component, more studies are needed to evaluate how well current information literacy programs address digital information challenges. There is also a need for empirical research linking information literacy with other competencies, such as information security awareness, to understand the broader implications of information literacy on students' digital behaviors and practices.

While information literacy remains a fundamental skill for directing the modern information studies, significant gaps in research and practice persist. Future studies should focus on evaluating the effectiveness of information literacy programs in various educational settings, integrating digital literacy into existing frameworks and exploring the connections between information literacy and other critical competencies. Addressing these gaps will contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of information literacy and its role in preparing students for success in the digital age.

Information security has become an essential field as digital technologies and online platforms increasingly pervade personal and educational areas. It covers a range of practices and principles aimed at protecting information from unauthorized access, disclosure, alteration, and destruction. The fundamental goals of information security are to ensure the confidentiality, integrity and availability of information (Grimes and Marquardson, 2019). As the volume and sensitivity of data continues to grow, the importance of robust information security measures has never been greater, particularly for undergraduate students who handle a substantial amount of personal and academic information.

Several theoretical frameworks provide a foundation for understanding information security. The CIA triad (Confidentiality, Integrity, and Availability) is a widely accepted model that defines the core objectives of information security. Additionally, the Risk Management Framework (RMF) focuses on identifying, assessing, and mitigating risks to information assets (NIST, 2018). These frameworks emphasize the need for a systematic approach to securing information and managing potential threats. They also highlight the importance of understanding and implementing security practices to protect information in various contexts, including academic environments.

In higher education, information security is critical due to the vast amounts of sensitive data handled by universities, including student records, research data and financial information. Despite the increasing awareness of information security, many institutions face challenges in effectively implementing security measures. Research has shown that universities often struggle with outdated security systems, insufficient training, and inadequate policies (Nieles, Dempsey and Pillitteri,

2017). This situation leaves students and staff vulnerable to security breaches and cyberattacks. Studies also indicate that while universities are improving their security infrastructure, there remains a need for more comprehensive training programs to enhance students' understanding of security practices (Kock, Berbekova, & Assaf, 2021).

The rise of digital technologies has introduced new security challenges, such as phishing attacks, malware, and social engineering threats. Digital security awareness involves recognizing these threats and implementing appropriate measures to mitigate them. According to research by Chu and Chau, (2014), individuals with high digital security awareness are better equipped to identify and respond to security threats. However, many undergraduate students lack adequate awareness and training, which increases their vulnerability to cyber threats. Effective digital security training programs are essential for improving students' ability to recognize and manage potential security risks (Aliyu, 2020).

A critical look at existing literature (Paul, 2022; Gwebu, Wangand Hu, 2020) reveals that while there is growing recognition of the importance of information security, significant challenges remain in its implementation and awareness. These studies consistently emphasize the need for effective security measures and training programs to protect sensitive information. However, according to Kock, Berbekova and Assaf (2021), there are gaps in the integration of comprehensive security awareness training within educational institutions. Furthermore, research often highlights a disconnect between theoretical knowledge and practical application, suggesting a need for more hands-on training and real-world simulations to enhance security awareness among students.

Gaps in the literature highlighted that there is limited research on the specific impact of information literacy on information security practices among university students. While there are various literature on information security awareness, its relationship with information literacy skills remains underexplored. Secondly, there is a need for more studies evaluating the effectiveness of current security training programs and their impact on students' security behaviors. Additionally, research is needed to investigate how different educational contexts and resource levels affect the implementation and efficacy of security measures.

From the existing literature, it can be deduced that while the field of information security has made significant strides, gaps in research and practice persist. Future studies should focus on exploring the intersection of information literacy and information security to understand how literacy skills influence security awareness and practices. Additionally, research should evaluate the effectiveness of security training programs and explore the impact of varying educational contexts on security outcomes. Addressing these gaps will contribute to more effective strategies for enhancing information security awareness and protecting sensitive data in academic settings.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a cross-sectional survey design to examine undergraduate students in Northern Nigeria. A multistage sampling technique was employed. At the first stage, a purposive sampling technique was used to select federal universities located specifically within the North-West region of Nigeria. At the second stage, a stratified random sampling technique was applied, with each stratum proportionally representing the total student population of the selected universities. The

overall undergraduate student population was 266,295. Based on Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) sample size determination table, a total of 346 respondents were selected for the study. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire designed to capture comprehensive information based on the objectives of the study. The collected data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistical methods. Descriptive statistics (such as frequencies, percentages, and mean scores) were used to summarize the data, highlight respondent characteristics, and provide insights into emerging trends and patterns. Inferential statistics, on the other hand, were applied to examine relationships between the variables, thereby enabling the study to draw valid generalizations and establish empirical links among the key variables under investigation.

Federal Universities in Northern Nigeria

Universities	No. of Students	Sample (n)
Ahmadu Bello University (ABU) Zaria	78,900	103
Bayero University Kano (BUK)	81,267	106
Federal University of Health Sciences, Sokoto (FUHS)	1,512	2
Federal University of Technology, Babura (FUTB)	2,256	3
Federal University, Birnin Kebbi (FUBK)	7,332	10
Federal University Dutse (FUD)	11,629	14
Federal University Dutsin-Ma (FUDMA)	8,912	12
Federal University Gusau (FUGUS)	6,871	9
Nigerian Defence Academy (NDA)	5,623	6
Usman Danfodio University Sokoto	61,993	81
Total population	266,295	346

RESULTS AND INTERPRETATIONS

A comprehensive survey was conducted, in which 346 questionnaires were distributed to the undergraduate students. Out of these, 236 questionnaires were successfully returned, achieving a notable response rate of 68.2%. This high response rate reflects a strong level of engagement from the respondents and ensures that the data collected is a representation of the target population. The returned questionnaires were carefully reviewed and found to be valuable for the research, providing a solid basis for thorough analysis and insightful interpretations. The substantial number of valid responses contributes to the reliability of the study's findings, offering a more accurate and in-depth understanding of the research topic.

Table 1: Level of Information literacy skills

S/N	Level of Literacy Skills	SA & A	UD	SD & D	Mean	Decision
1	I have the ability to formulate questions based on my information needs even if I don't know where the information is located	121 (51.2%)	26 (10.9%)	89 (37.8%)	3.2	Accepted
2	I have the ability to recognize a need for information resources	200 (84.8%)	26 (10.8%)	10 (4.4%)	4.17	Accepted
3	I have the ability to distinguish potential information resources	213 (90.3%)	11 (4.6%)	12 (5.1%)	4.28	Accepted
4	I have the ability to recognize different methods of accessing information sources and resources	44 (18.7%)	11 (4.6%)	181 (76.7%)	2.10	Rejected
5	I have the ability to recognize vagueness in the search process	71 (30.1%)	11 (4.6%)	154 (65.4%)	2.50	Accepted
6	I have the ability to use information in critical thinking and problem solving	213 (90.3%)	5 (1.9%)	18 (7.8%)	4.30	Accepted
7	I have the ability to organize, apply and communicate information	78 (33.2%)	16 (6.8%)	142 (60.0%)	2.60	Accepted
8	I have the ability to synthesize and build on existing information	8 (3.2%)	15 (6.5%)	213 (90.3%)	1.80	Rejected
9	I have the ability to browse online and offline databases to locate pertinent information	105 (44.7%)	10 (4.2%)	121 (51.0%)	2.91	Accepted
10	I have the ability to construct strategies for locating information	57 (23.9%)	6 (2.6%)	173 (73.4%)	2.30	Rejected
11	I have the ability to decide when to adopt emerging innovations in ICT	119 (50.6%)	7 (2.9%)	110 (46.5%)	3.10	Accepted
12	I have the ability to integrate new information into an existing body of knowledge	24 (10.3%)	5 (1.9%)	207 (87.8%)	1.85	Rejected
13	I have the ability to evaluate information obtained from different sources	12 (5.1%)	17 (7.3%)	207 (87.7%)	1.70	Rejected

Key: SA (Strongly Agreed), A (Agreed), UD (Undecided), D (Disagreed) & SD (Strongly Disagreed):
 Acceptance rule: If the mean $\geq 2.5 \rightarrow$ Accept (respondents generally agree). If the mean $< 2.4 \rightarrow$
 Reject (respondents generally disagree).

The analysis of the table highlights both strengths and areas for improvement in the information literacy skills of undergraduate students. A notable strength is in question formulation and recognition of information needs. A significant portion of students (51.2%) demonstrated the ability to formulate questions based on their needs, and an even higher percentage (84.8%) recognized when they needed information resources. This suggests that students have a good foundational understanding of identifying and articulating their information requirements, which is crucial for academic inquiry and research.

However, there are concerning gaps in students' abilities to navigate and access various information sources. Despite a high competency in distinguishing between different information resources (90.3%), only 18.7% of students agreed they could recognize different methods of accessing these sources, with a majority (76.7%) disagreeing. This indicates a disconnect between the students' awareness of available resources and their ability to effectively locate and utilize

them. This gap suggests a need for enhanced instruction in information retrieval skills, particularly in navigating digital databases and library catalogs.

Critical thinking and the application of information also showed positive results, with 90.3% of students expressing confidence in these areas. This skill is fundamental for academic success, as it enables students to analyze, synthesize, and apply information effectively. However, the lower scores in areas related to organizing and communicating information, and integrating new information into existing knowledge, point to potential deficiencies in higher-order information skills. These findings indicate a need for targeted interventions in information literacy programs to strengthen these crucial skills, thereby enabling students to engage more deeply with academic content and contribute to scholarly discourse.

Table 2: Awareness of Information Security Practices

S/N	Item	VHE	HE	LE	NA	Mean
1	I understand strong password creation and maintenance practices, such as complexity, regular changes, and avoiding reuse.	109 (46.2%)	10 (4.2%)	0 (0%)	117 (49.6%)	3.9160
2	I have the ability to recognize phishing attempts through emails, links, or websites, and understanding how to respond appropriately.	149 (63.1%)	43 (18.2%)	13 (5.5%)	31 (13.1%)	3.4202
3	I am aware of data privacy issues, including the importance of protecting personal information and understanding privacy settings on digital platforms.	153 (64.8%)	30 (12.7%)	13 (5.5%)	40 (17.0%)	3.2521
4	I have knowledge of secure browsing practices, such as identifying secure websites (HTTPS), using incognito mode, and avoiding public Wi-Fi for sensitive activities.	161 (68.2%)	23 (9.7%)	15 (6.4%)	37 (15.7%)	3.2269
5	I am aware of the importance of regularly updating software, operating systems, and applications to protect against vulnerabilities.	139 (58.9%)	5 (2.1%)	70 (29.7%)	22 (9.3%)	2.5294
6	I understand social engineering tactics used to manipulate individuals into revealing confidential information and strategies to avoid them.	148 (62.7%)	55 (23.3%)	0 (0%)	33 (14.0%)	3.1597
7	I am familiar with the use of security tools such as antivirus software, firewalls, and encryption to protect digital devices and data.	105 (44.5%)	45 (19.1%)	61 (25.8%)	25 (10.6%)	2.9513

Key: VHE (Very High Extent), HE (High Extent), LE (Low Extent), and NA (Not Applicable)
Acceptance rule: If the mean $\geq 2.5 \rightarrow$ Accept (respondents generally agree). If the mean $< 2.4 \rightarrow$ Reject (respondents generally disagree).

The analysis of the table reveals several key understandings into the information security awareness and practices among the respondents. The first item, regarding the understanding of strong password creation and maintenance, shows a relatively balanced awareness, with 46.2% of respondents indicating a very high extent of understanding and 49.6% finding it not applicable. This suggests that while a significant portion of the respondents are aware of best practices for password security, a substantial number may not see the relevance of this knowledge, possibly indicating a gap in practical application or engagement with these practices.

In the second item, concerning the ability to recognize phishing attempts, 63.1% of respondents reported a very high extent of awareness, which is encouraging as it indicates a strong recognition of a common security threat. However, the 13.1% of respondents who marked this as not applicable suggests a need for further education and training to ensure that all individuals are adequately equipped to identify and respond to phishing attempts. This pattern is consistent across other items, such as the awareness of data privacy issues (64.8% very high extent) and secure browsing practices (68.2% very high extent), indicating a generally high level of awareness among the respondents about fundamental aspects of information security.

However, the analysis also highlights areas needing improvement, particularly in keeping software and systems updated, as indicated by only 58.9% acknowledging this to a very high extent and 29.7% at a low extent. This suggests a significant knowledge gap or neglect in maintaining up-to-date systems, which is crucial for protecting against vulnerabilities. Additionally, the understanding of social engineering tactics and the use of security tools such as antivirus software, while relatively high, still shows room for enhancement, especially with a notable proportion of respondents (25.8%) not extensively familiar with using security tools. This analysis underscores the need for targeted educational initiatives to bolster comprehensive information security awareness and practices among the respondents.

Correlation between Information Literacy Skills and Information Security Practices **Regression Analysis of Utilization and influence of e-resources**

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	-5.325	.680		-7.825	.000
Level of Information Literacy	2.442	.186	.772	13.143	.000

a. Information Security Practices

Table 3.0 represents the linear regression analysis of level of information literacy and information security practices. The analysis on the table revealed that the correlation is significant with 0.01 level of confidence and is positive with $r = 0.772$ correlation coefficient. That shows a very strong significant relationship between level of information Literacy and information security practices. The analysis shows that a unit increase in level of information Literacy will lead to more enhanced and information security practices by the undergraduate students.

The table further revealed the unstandardized Beta (B) column value of 2.442 which is the slope of line of interception and an indicator of the level of effect the predictor independent variable (level of information Literacy) has on the dependent variable (information security practices). In practice it means; an average increase in level of Information Literacy will lead to 2.442 increases in information security practices. A 5% increase in level of information Literacy will lead to (5×2.442) 12 unit's increase in the information security practices of undergraduate students.

According to Bornmann and Leydesdoff (2013) if the P value significant level is less than 0.05 ($p < .05$) then the Null Hypothesis of the study will be rejected while if the P value significant level is greater than 0.05 ($p > .05$) the Null Hypothesis of the study will be retained. Therefore, according to the analysis presented on table 3.0, the H_0 is rejected ($p < 0.05$ i.e. Sig = 0.00), because there is sufficient evidence of significant correlation between level of information Literacy and information security practices. The variations in the mean of information Literacy on enhancing information security practices are not happening by chance but as a result of the influence and intervention of the independent variable "Information Literacy". Therefore, there is a statistically significant correlation between information Literacy and the information security practices undergraduate students.

DISCUSSION

The study reveals a complex interplay between information literacy skills and information security practices among undergraduate students. The findings indicate that students generally exhibit strong foundational abilities in identifying their information needs, formulating relevant questions, and applying information for critical thinking and problem-solving. These skills are essential for academic success and demonstrate a solid understanding of basic information literacy concepts. However, the study also uncovers significant gaps in students' ability to navigate information sources effectively and integrate new information into their existing knowledge, suggesting a need for more advanced training in these areas.

In terms of information security, the study highlights a commendable level of awareness regarding fundamental practices such as password management, recognizing phishing attempts, and understanding data privacy. Nonetheless, there are notable shortcomings in students' familiarity with more sophisticated security measures, including regular software updates and the use of security tools. This discrepancy points to a critical need for enhanced educational initiatives that address both basic and advanced aspects of information security, ensuring students are well-equipped to protect their digital assets effectively.

The correlation between information literacy and security practices underscores the importance of integrating comprehensive training in both areas. Students with higher information literacy skills tend to exhibit better security practices, yet there remains room for improvement in both domains. By focusing on targeted interventions and practical applications, educational programs can better prepare students to navigate and secure information in an increasingly digital world. Strengthening these skills will not only enhance students' academic performance but also their ability to manage and protect information in their future careers.

The analysis of the tables reveals a significant correlation between information literacy skills and information security practices among undergraduate students. High levels of literacy skills, particularly in recognizing the need for information resources, distinguishing potential resources, and using information in critical thinking, directly correlate with an understanding of essential information security practices. For instance, a substantial 84.8% of respondents could recognize a need for information resources, with a corresponding 63.1% demonstrating a strong ability to recognize phishing attempts. This suggests that students who are well-versed in identifying and accessing necessary information resources are more likely to be equipped to identify and mitigate security threats like phishing.

Furthermore, the ability to synthesize and build on existing information—a critical literacy skill—was notably low, with only 3.2% of respondents showing proficiency in this area. This deficit correlates with a lack of understanding in more nuanced information security practices, such as using secure browsing methods or maintaining software updates. Only 58.9% of respondents were aware of the importance of regular updates, indicating that gaps in advanced literacy skills can lead to vulnerabilities in information security awareness. This highlights the need for more comprehensive training in both information literacy and security practices, emphasizing the integration and application of new information.

Moreover, the data reveals a significant discrepancy in the understanding of basic versus advanced information security practices. While a majority of respondents displayed a strong understanding of fundamental practices, such as password management and recognizing phishing attempts, there was a notable lack of familiarity with more advanced security measures. For example, familiarity with using security tools like antivirus software and encryption was moderate, with only 44.5% expressing confidence. This discrepancy underscores the need for targeted educational initiatives that not only cover basic security practices but also address more advanced topics, ensuring that students are fully equipped to protect their digital assets.

In summary, the relationship between information literacy skills and security practices is evident, with higher literacy levels generally leading to better security practices. However, the data also indicates areas where both literacy and security awareness need significant improvement. Enhanced educational programs focusing on both literacy skills and practical security measures are crucial for bridging these gaps. Such initiatives would not only improve individual student capabilities but also contribute to a more secure academic environment overall.

CONCLUSION

The research findings reveal a nuanced picture of information literacy and security practices among undergraduate students. The results show that students generally possess strong foundational skills in recognizing information needs, formulating questions, and applying information for critical thinking and problem-solving. However, there are notable gaps in their abilities to navigate information sources effectively and integrate new information into existing knowledge. These gaps underscore the need for improved instruction in advanced information retrieval techniques and higher-order skills necessary for academic and professional success.

On the information security front, students display a solid understanding of fundamental security practices, such as password creation, recognizing phishing attempts, and data privacy. However, there are areas requiring significant attention, particularly in the consistent application of software updates and the use of advanced security tools. The disparity between high awareness of basic practices and lower familiarity with more sophisticated security measures highlights the necessity for more comprehensive education in information security.

The correlation between information literacy and security practices suggests that students with higher literacy skills are better equipped to handle information security threats. Nevertheless, the study indicates that both literacy and security awareness need targeted improvements. By integrating enhanced training in both domains, educational programs can better prepare students to navigate and protect their digital environments effectively, thereby fostering a more secure and informed academic community.

RECOMMENDATION

1. Integrate Advanced Literacy Training: Include advanced information literacy skills in the curriculum and offer workshops focusing on search strategies and critical evaluation.
2. Enhance Security Education: Implement comprehensive training on both basic and advanced security practices, with regular updates on new threats and tools.
3. Apply and Assess Skills: Use real-world scenarios and regular assessments to reinforce practical application of information literacy and security skills.
4. Leverage Expert Collaboration: Partner with information security and library professionals to enrich training and provide expert insights.
5. Encourage Continuous Learning: Promote ongoing learning and provide resources for students to stay updated on information literacy and security practices.

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